

Deep Learning with Convolutional Neural Network for Proportional Control of Finger Movements from surface EMG Recordings

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Abstract— The control of robotic prosthetic hands (RPHs) for upper limb amputees is far from optimal. Simultaneous and proportional finger control of a RPH based on EMG signals is still challenging. Based on EMG and kinematics recordings of subjects following a pre-defined sequence of single and multi-fingers movements, we aimed at predicting finger flexion and thumb opposition angles. We compared two deep learning (DL) based approaches, the first one using the raw EMG signals and the second one using the spectrogram of the signal as input, with the standard state of the art decoding technique (STD) for finger angle regression. Using a genetic algorithm for hyper-parameter optimization, we obtained an optimized model architecture (and set of features in the case of STD) for each condition on one recording session. Then, we evaluated the best model of each condition on the eleven EMG and finger kinematics recordings available from four subjects. The two DL approaches based on convolutional neural networks predicted finger angles with a similar mean squared error loss but both of them outperformed the standard approach for the regression of simultaneous single-finger angles. This proposed decoding strategy and hyper-parameter optimization framework provides a basis to further improve single finger proportional control for RPHs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Controlling the human hand feels simple and intuitive but relies on a sophisticated and robust control strategy that allows for dexterous manipulation of a variety of objects. Hand loss is a traumatic event with not only motor but also psychological consequences [1], resulting in limited ability to perform object manipulation, sensing, as well as non-verbal communication. Robotic Prosthetic Hands (RPHs) aim at restoring hand functionality in trans-radial amputees. In order to capture the user's intention, these RPHs usually rely on electromyographic (EMG) signals recorded from their residual forearm muscle activity. Commercially available RPHs usually use two surface EMG (sEMG) electrodes placed on remaining antagonist muscles (usually wrist flexion/extension). The control of these robotic hands rely on a simple threshold based strategy controlling one degree of freedom [2]. The type of grasp can be selected using co-contraction to cycle between pre-defined grasps.

By using more electrodes (~6-8), pattern recognition algorithms are an alternative to this direct control approach. It consists of extracting discriminative features from the EMG signals to decode directly the type of grasp intended by the user. After a calibration phase, the user only has to think to perform the desired grasp with his phantom hand. Results

showed 98% accuracy on 4 classes [3] and up to 75% for 50 classes [4]. Other groups showed the possibility to decode single finger flexion and extension [5] with performance of 99% accuracy on single and multi-finger movements.

Although this approach is more intuitive, it is still different from the natural way of controlling finger. Indeed, to obtain fingers in a middle position, the user has to contract his muscles until the desired angle is reached then relax to keep the RPH in the same position. In order to obtain an even more natural control, few groups showed the possibility to perform single finger proportional control performing angle regression instead of movement classification [6]–[8].

To decode meaningful information from EMG data, it is necessary to transform the signals into informative, discriminating and independent features. It has been now several decades that researchers have been working on the design of the best features to decode motor intentions from EMG signals [9]. Since the first example in 2016 [10], the EMG decoding community shifted from this standard feature engineering (STD) approach to feature learning approach using deep learning (DL) and in most cases convolutional neural networks (CNN). The standard deep networks usually consists of several convolutional layers followed by fully-connected layers [11]. Convolutional layers can learn discriminative features from the input signal and reduce its dimension. These features are then used as input to the fully connected layers that will make the prediction (see Figure 1). For EMG decoding, the input of CNNs can be either the raw signal [12] or the spectrogram of the signal [13]. Several studies showed that deep networks could learn more discriminative features directly from the raw signal to perform grasp classification with higher accuracies than STD [14], [15]. Few groups showed DL-based regression of motor intention using sEMG for arm [16] and wrist motion [17]–[19] with promising results. For a more extensive review on RPHs see [20].

The “perfect” motor decoding strategy could be described as one that increases subject dexterity to a level comparable to the healthy hand. In order to be as close as possible to the natural control of the hand, one have to decode fingers angle continuously and simultaneously. Due to the higher performance of DL compared to the STD approach in grasp classification, we aimed at quantifying the performance of single finger proportional control with a DL vs STD approach.

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Figure 1. Training paradigm difference between a STD approach and Deep learning (dashed objects represents tunable hyper parameters).

II. METHODS

A. EMG Dataset and pre-processing

The detailed protocol for EMG acquisition comes from Zhuang et al. (2019) experiment 3 [21]. Briefly, four healthy subjects aged between 20 and 26 were recruited for this experiment. Ethical approval was obtained by the cantonal ethical committee of Vaud. Informed consent was obtained from all participants in the study. The subjects participated to 2 or 3 calibration sessions where EMG signals were recorded using a Noraxon Delsys system connected to a LabJack data acquisition card to record six channels placed around the subject’s forearm on specific muscles corresponding to the flexion of each finger and thumb opposition found with palpation. In this article, we focus only on the offline calibration part of the decoding model. The subjects followed a series of movements on a screen performed in a virtual environment. Hand kinematics were obtained from the finger angles shown on the video. The movements consisted in single and multi-finger movements and the virtual environment was synchronized with the EMG acquisition setup. The sequence of movements was repeated 5 times, each

Figure 2. Illustration of the movements present in the EMG recordings. with a hold period of 5 seconds and the total time of the video

was 4.5 minutes (see Figure 1). The EMG signals were recorded at 2 kHz and the kinematics at 60 Hz.

From the 15 joint angles recorded during the training phase on the virtual environment, six joint angles were selected: the metacarpophalangeal joint angle of each finger to estimate finger flexion/extension and the carpometacarpal joint angle for thumb opposition. Kinematic data was linearly interpolated and oversampled at 2 kHz to match the EMG signal sampling frequency. The dataset was then split into train, validation and test set, the three first repetitions were used for the training set, one for the validation set and the last one for testing. This non-random split was done to consider the real-world use case of RPH. Indeed, amputees would use their RPH after this calibration phase and therefore the last repetition for testing is the most suited repetition to evaluate performance of the decoding in real world scenario. For each set, a sliding window of 192ms with a moving step of 40ms (152ms overlap) was used, the angle values of the end of each window were kept as labels and the angles were rescaled between 0 (fully open) and 10 (fully flexed).

B. Learning paradigms

In order to quantify the performance of DL vs STD, three learning paradigms are compared: The standard feature engineering approach (STD), a DL approach with the raw signal as input (RAW) and a DL approach with the spectrogram computed with the fast Fourier transform of each individual window (FFT) as input. For the two DL approaches, the input signal window is reshaped as squared images as in [22]. In the STD one, EMG signals are processed and features are extracted from each channel. We chose 9 well-explored time and frequency domain features to extract from each time window [23]:

1. Mean Absolute Value
2. Wavelength: Cumulative length of waveform over time
3. Maximum Absolute Value

4. Standard Deviation
5. Zero Crossings: Number of times the signal crosses zero
6. Slope sign changes: Number of time that the slope of the EMG signal changes sign
7. Root Mean Square
8. Log detector: $e^{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log(|x_i|)}$ where x_i is the EMG amplitude at time bin i .
9. Frequency spectrums in each frequency bin between 7 and 12 Hz, 12-30, 30-50, 50-100, 100-150 and 150-400 Hz from FFT results.

C. Hyper-parameter optimization

There is a high number of hyper-parameters to optimize for each paradigm. Among those, we optimized a set of parameters based on the first session of the first subject due to computational power required to perform a hyper-parameter search for each recording. The hypothesis being that the quantity of information is relatively the same for each recording and therefore, the complexity of the dataset is relatively the same, meaning that the best model architecture for one recording is a good model for the other recordings.

For the two DL approaches (RAW and FFT), we started from a VGG-like architecture [24] and optimized the shape of the network: the number of convolutional layers before each average pooling layer (up to 3), the number of pooling layer (up to 5) and the number of filters for each convolutional layer (16, 32, 64, 128). A batch-normalization layer follows each convolutional layer. Then, the number of fully connected layers (up to two layers) and the number of nodes for each layer (16, 32, 64) were also tuned. Except from the architectural parameter, the drop rate was also optimized (0, 0.2, 0.5) as well as the L_2 regularization rate (0, $1e-3$, 0.1), the learning rate (0.1, 0.01, 0.001), the convolutional filter size in x dimension, in y dimension (1, 3, 5) and the padding strategy for image border (with or without). The CNN networks were optimized with a batch gradient descent with a batch size of 32 samples, with 50 epochs, a step decay with a drop of $\frac{1}{2}$ every 10 epochs and an early stopping if the validation loss did not decreased for more than 13 epochs.

For the STD approach, the model was a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) and therefore has less parameters to tune. However, the feature selection is an important process in order not to overfit the data. Therefore the hyper-parameters were the selection or not of a feature, the number of fully connected layers (up to 3 hidden layers), the number of node per layer (16, 32, 64, 128, 256), the drop rate (0, 0.2, 0.5), the L_1 and L_2 regularization terms (0, $1e-3$, 0.1), the learning rate (0.1, 0.01, 0.001) and the optimizer (Adam, RMSprop, batch gradient descent). The MLP was optimized with a batch gradient descent with a batch size of 16 samples, with 100 epochs and similarly to the CNN, a step decay with a drop of $\frac{1}{2}$ every 10 epochs with an early stopping if the validation loss did not decreased for more than 13 epochs. All the models were trained with a mean squared error loss (MSE).

Due to the high dimensionality of the hyper-parameter space, a grid search was impossible to perform in a reasonable amount of time. Therefore, we opted for a genetic algorithm (GA) parameter optimization approach [25]. The problem was formulated as a genetic representation of the solution domain

where each hyper-parameter was encoded as a gene on a chromosome that could take one of the discrete possible values. The fitness function was encoded as the validation loss of the trained model to evaluate the solution domain. A population of 20 random individual was created and trained for 200 generation using a fitness proportionate (or roulette wheel) offspring selection method. The rate of mutation was set to 0.1 and the selection rate to 0.6.

D. Performance evaluation of each subject

After hyper-parameter optimization on one session, the same pre-processing steps will be applied to all the available recordings in order to train a model on each recording available. For each recording, the model was trained ten times and the model with the lowest validation loss is kept. This step was necessary to reduce the chances of having the model stuck in a local minimum. Then the best model was evaluated on the testing set.

Figure 3. Architecture of the best model

III. RESULTS

The best model for the three paradigms obtained with the genetic algorithms was with RAW condition and had a validation loss of 5.34 and a training loss of 2.20. The model architecture is shown in Figure 3. It is strained with a drop rate of 50%, without L_2 normalization, a learning rate of 0.01 and the shape of the convolutional mask is (3, 1) with 0 padding to keep the same output dimension.

Figure 4. Boxplots of the test loss over all sessions for the best model with RAW, FFT and STD conditions

For the FFT condition, the minimum validation loss was 6.41 with a training loss of 4.82 and for STD, the minimum validation loss was 9.14 with a training loss of 9.43. For the STD model, features from all channels were extracted and the final model used all the features except the slope sign change for a total of 46 features.

The average test loss, meaning the performance on unseen data, per condition is shown in Figure 4 for the 11 sessions. The STD test loss is significantly different from the two other conditions (t-test, $p < 0.05$) but the FFT and RAW conditions are not different.

The test loss for each subject is shown in Figure 5, each subject recorded 3 sessions except S2 who did only two calibration sessions. An example of the predicted angles versus the target labels is shown in Figure 6 for the RAW condition on the test set of subject S1. It consist of one repetition of each movement and lasts for 56 seconds. The angles correspond to the sequence: Index Flexion, Middle Finger Flexion, Ring Finger Flexion, Ulnar Grasp, Open, Tridigital Grasp, Power Grasp, Thumb opposition and Thumb opposition + flexion. It corresponds to a loss of 7.36. The baseline loss corresponding to a model outputting only the mean value of the targets was ~ 19 .

Figure 5. Barplot of the test loss per subject for the best model with RAW, FFT and STD conditions

IV. DISCUSSION

This work aimed at quantifying the performance of DL compared to a STD feature extraction approach. The results showed that both DL conditions (RAW and FFT) are performing better than STD. However, it is not possible to conclude on which approach between RAW and FFT is best suited for single finger proportional control. For simplicity, one could argue to keep the RAW condition to avoid computing the FFT and therefore reduce the computational time for real time applications. A possible optimization is the combination of time-frequency information merging the RAW and FFT approaches, increasing the amount of information that inputs the model.

However, the amount of data per session in these experiments is relatively low (3 repetitions for the train set) which create uncertainty during the training of the different models and high differences between the validation and testing losses.

Figure 6. Plot of the predicted angles (orange) vs. target angles of the test set. X-axis is shared across columns

Another limitation to take into account is that the dataset comprised only fully open and closed positions held for several seconds without any real “rest/middle” position or other arbitrary angles. Indeed, when the users follow movements shown on a screen, there are intrinsic delays due to their reaction time that create jitter between expected kinematics and actual finger positions. In the case of single finger proportional control, exact finger position is paramount. Therefore, obtaining synchronized middle values is challenging and may be obtained using a kinematic glove for example.

Deep networks like CNNs need a huge amount of data to reach their maximum accuracy (e.g. ImageNet Challenge [26]) which means that increasing the amount of data could play a significant role in the performances obtained. However, a subject cannot reasonably record tens of hours of data in a single sitting. One possible solution is to leverage the information of several subjects to pre-train a general network that could be fine-tuned for the subject’s specific EMG activity. Several authors [13], [27], [28] investigated this approach and showed promising results for grasp classification, this strategy could be applied to single finger proportional control.

V. CONCLUSION

To conclude, we showed that deep learning is a promising approach for proportional EMG decoding. Due to the placement of the electrodes on the forearm, these results obtained on healthy subjects could apply for trans-radial amputees or amputations that are more distal. On the decoding side, we cannot conclude on the best DL approach between raw signals or spectrogram as input since both outperformed the standard state-of-the-art approach but were not statistically different.

For future developments, increasing the amount of data should be the main objective. Leveraging open access EMG databases like NinaPro [29], [30] to improve performances of DL for single-finger regression. The feasibility of this DL approach in real time to control a real prosthesis or any microprocessor should also be addressed due to the high computational cost of the models used.

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